

YOGA PRANA VIDYA (YPV) HEALING AS A COMPLEMENTARY THERAPY FOR MYOPIA: A CLINICAL CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Myopia, or nearsightedness, is a common refractive error where distant objects appear blurred while near vision remains clear. Although usually manageable with corrective lenses, progressive myopia may lead to complications. Complementary therapies such as Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing are being explored for supportive benefits. **Method:** A 23-year-old female with a history of short-sightedness since birth underwent YPV healing sessions by a Senior Healer and Trainer for 15 days. **Results:** The patient reported noticeable improvement in her distant vision after the healing sessions, which was subsequently confirmed by ophthalmological evaluation. **Conclusion:** YPV healing may serve as an effective complementary therapy in improving vision and managing long-standing conditions such as myopia.

KEYWORDS: Yoga Prana Vidya System®, Myopia, energy healing, Refractive error, Complementary therapy, Vision improvement.

INTRODUCTION

As emphasized by an Ayurvedic *Āchārya*, the eyes—the organs of sight—are regarded as the most important among the five sense organs, especially for human beings. Vision plays a central role in perceiving and interacting with the world, and therefore continuous efforts must be made to preserve it throughout life. For a person who is blind, the external world appears the same, with no distinction between day and night. No matter how much wealth or material possessions one may have, the beauty and richness of the world lose their meaning without the gift of sight.^[1]

Myopia, commonly referred to as short-sightedness, is the most prevalent eye disorder worldwide and carries substantial social, educational, and economic impact.^[2] Globally, its prevalence has been steadily increasing and is projected to affect nearly 50% of the world's population by 2050.^{[3],[4]} In India, studies have reported prevalence among schoolchildren ranging from 7–17%, with urban populations showing higher rates compared to rural counterparts.^{[5],[6]}

The development of myopia is influenced by multiple factors. Genetic predisposition plays an important role through various biochemical pathways, while structural weaknesses of the sclera and cornea have also been identified as significant contributors. Environmental and lifestyle factors further accelerate progression. Additionally, nutritional deficiencies, stress, chronic illnesses, and endocrine imbalances can affect overall growth and may indirectly influence the course of myopia.^[7]

The socioeconomic burden of myopia is considerable. Billions of dollars are spent annually worldwide on corrective measures, including spectacles, contact lenses, and surgical interventions. Although surgical options such as LASIK are increasingly popular, they are not universally successful and may be associated with complications such as dry eyes and night glare.^[8] While modern ophthalmology has made tremendous advances in diagnosis and treatment, the limitations and side effects of current approaches highlight the need to explore safe, non-invasive complementary therapies.

In this context, Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV)—a no-touch, no-drug, integrated, holistic and complimentary energy healing system—emerges as a promising supportive modality in the management of long-standing conditions such as myopia. YPV has been established as a structured discipline for addressing a wide range of physiological and psychological ailments.^[9] It is widely practiced as a complementary therapy alongside mainstream systems of medicine such as Allopathy, Ayurveda, and Homeopathy, and in certain cases has been successfully applied as a standalone approach.^{[10][11]}

Growing scientific literature (including over 125 published research papers) provides supportive evidence of its effectiveness. Case studies have documented significant clinical improvements across diverse conditions: normalization of thyroid function in hypothyroidism^[9], restoration of menstruation and hormonal balance in polycystic ovarian syndrome^[12], accelerated recovery following subarachnoid hemorrhage^[13] and substantial re-pigmentation in vitiligo through sustained self-healing practice.^[14] Collectively, these reports highlight YPV's potential as a safe, cost-effective, and integrative modality that can complement conventional medical care or serve as a standalone therapeutic intervention in selected cases.

CASE HISTORY

A 23-year-old female presented with complaints of short-sightedness (myopia) since birth, which was clinically noted at the age of 3 years. Her current refractive error was -3.00 D in the right eye and -3.25 D in the left eye. She had no significant past medical history or family history of ocular disorders. The patient had been using corrective lenses for visual correction.

The patient was introduced to Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing by her mother, who is a trained healer and Arhat yogi. Seeking complementary approaches for the management of her condition, she participated in a YPV training workshop that involved the use of crystals, conducted by a senior YPV healer and Arhat Trainer. During a healing class on 21st August 2014, she received her first demonstration healing session specifically for myopia, marking the initiation of her exposure to YPV healing.

YPV HEALING PROTOCOL

The patient underwent 15 days of daily healing sessions that included YPV Psychotherapy, YPV Advanced Healing using color prana, and Healer Development Program (HDP) Level 1 with a special focus on eyesight regeneration.

1. YPV Level 3 (Psychotherapy)

Since physical ailments often have a psychological component and vice versa, psychotherapy was considered essential. Chakras are known to regulate both

physical and psychological functions by supplying energy to various organs and systems. Hence, psychological healing was conducted prior to physical healing.^[15]

- The YPV Psychotherapy protocol involved treatment of the following chakras:
 - Front and back Heart chakra
 - Front and back Solar Plexus chakra
 - Throat chakra
 - Ajna chakra
 - Crown chakra
 - Sex chakra
 - Basic chakra
- This process was followed in all 15 days healing sessions.

2. YPV Level 2 (Advanced Healing using Color Prana)
Advanced healing was carried out using specific color pranas to intensify the healing effect. The protocol included.

- General cleansing of the energy body
- Blood cleansing technique
- Internal organ technique
- Thorough cleansing, energizing, and balancing of all relevant chakras
- This was performed in all 15 sessions.

3. Healer Development Program (HDP) – Level 1

As part of HDP Level 1, the special eye sight regeneration technique was applied to the patient. This was practiced during all healing sessions to address her myopia.

RESULTS

After the first day of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing, the patient's refractive error showed measurable improvement, reducing to -2.50 D in the right eye and -2.75 D in the left eye. Following the third consecutive day of healing, her refractive error further improved to -2.25 D in both eyes. Subsequently, she continued with 12 additional healing sessions. On 4th September 2014, a formal ophthalmological evaluation confirmed her refractive error as -2.00 D in both eyes, as documented in the attached ophthalmologist's report.

DISCUSSION

Myopia is a common refractive error that typically requires corrective lenses, and in some cases surgical or pharmacological interventions, for management. Conventional medicine offers symptomatic relief but has limited options for natural regression of myopia. In this case, the patient demonstrated measurable improvement in refractive error following first three consecutive sessions of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing, which combined psychotherapy, advanced healing using color prana, and Healer Development Program (HDP) Level 1 for eyesight regeneration.

The observed reduction from -3.00/-3.25 D to -2.00 D in total of 15 healing sessions indicates the potential role of YPV healing in improving ocular energy balance and promoting functional correction. Psychotherapy addressed underlying emotional and psychological factors, while advanced energy healing and color prana techniques facilitated cleansing and energizing of the chakras associated with the visual system. The HDP eyesight regeneration protocol specifically targeted the eyes, contributing to progressive improvement.

These findings are consistent with previously published evidence. It was reported that the vision improvements in participants of a two-week YPV eye camp, where 23 out of 27 patients showed 80-100% improvement in visual function, with several able to read without spectacles after 5-10 days of healing.^[16] Such corroborative evidence supports the hypothesis that YPV healing may positively influence refractive conditions like myopia.

CONCLUSION

This case highlights the potential of Yoga Prana Vidya healing as a supportive complementary therapy in the management of chronic conditions such as myopia. While conventional ophthalmic care remains essential, YPV healing may provide additional benefits in improving visual outcomes and enhancing overall well-

being. Further studies with larger cohorts, control groups, and long-term follow-up are needed to validate these findings and establish YPV as a complementary therapy in managing refractive errors such as myopia.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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